

Effects of Corrosive Environments on Graphite/Epoxy Composites

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ABSTRACT

The effects on fatigue life of short term exposure of T300/934 and AS/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composite specimens to various environmental contaminants such as jet fuel, hydraulic fluid, and salt water are presented. Different contaminants are shown to produce significant changes in fatigue life, some reducing life and some increasing life. Long term exposure effects on the fatigue life, modulus and compressive strength of AS/3501-6 specimens to similar contaminants and temperature-humidity cycling are also presented.

INTRODUCTION

Use of graphite/epoxy composites in aircraft primary structural areas such as a center wing box, wing structure, or fuselage depends greatly on the environmental compatibility of these laminates to several potential contaminants such as jet fuel, hydraulic fluid, cleaners, and salt water. This would be particularly critical for Naval applications such as V/STOL or sea siter incorporating such materials. Not only are advanced composites of interest to aircraft designers, their utility for weight-reduction has attracted ship designer interest. Exploratory programs for the U.S. Navy have been initiated to develop and certify a variety of advanced composites such as glass, graphite, and boron in a resinous matrix. Response of a composite material in service to contaminants should be a cumulative effect of possible plasticization of the matrix or matrix/fiber interface bond degradation, but without fiber damage. Of primary importance is an evaluation of whether any of these contaminants produce a change in laminate stiffness. Because of the high cost of real time fatigue testing but with the need for long term exposure effects this investigation was broken down into both short term and long term effects. Short term tests in fatigue were conducted at 1 and 3 Hz at a stress level to give a life at least 10^5 cycles. Long term testing consisted of unloaded static exposure of specimens to a contaminant for up to four years followed by static compression and/or tension-compression fatigue. Long term tests reported herein only include the first 2 years with other specimens continuing in exposure. Two graphite/epoxy laminates were evaluated T300/934 and AS/3501-6.

TEST SPECIMEN DESIGN

All specimens in this program were cut from .914 x 1.22m inch quasi-isotropic (0/45/90/-45_s/90/45/0)_s panels into two types of parallel sided unnotched specimens: 267 mm long by 22 mm wide with 152 mm gage lengths, and 533

mm long by 76 mm wide with 381 mm gage lengths. The 76 mm wide specimens were only used for tension-tension fatigue tests and were fabricated only from T300/934 panels. Since the tensile strength has been shown to be fiber controlled^[2,3] and essentially no strength losses have been reported for environmentally exposed tensile specimens, subsequent fatigue tests were conducted in tension-compression loading on the smaller 22 mm wide specimens in both T300/934 and AS/3501-6. Specimen grip tabs were 8 plies of 1581 glass/fabric/epoxy 1.78 mm thick bonded to the specimen with FM400 adhesive.

TEST PROCEDURES

Static compression tests were performed on 22 mm wide specimens with 152 mm gage lengths using a 16 pin 8.8 mm column length buckling restraint fixture shown in Figure 1. Specimens were gripped in self-aligning hydraulic grips. Strain was measured by attaching a two inch gage length extensometer to the specimen edges. Loading was at a rate of 1.3 mm/minute.

Fatigue testing was accomplished using computer controlled closed-loop electrohydraulic axial testing machines with friction bolt type grips. Specimens run in tension-tension fatigue had no form of buckling restraint and the minimum load set such that no localized buckling occurred until delamination onset. Specimens run in tension-compression had two cross bar buckling restraints placed at 1/3 span points as shown in Figure 2. These were coated with teflon tape and set finger tight.

Tension-tension ($R=0.06$) fatigue tests were conducted on T300/934 in both a circulating 3-1/2% NaCl solution and a phosphate ester hydraulic fluid (Skydrol LD4) using 3-inch wide specimens. A 305 mm long plexiglass chamber was attached with silicone rubber to the center test section of specimens. For the tests with Skydrol the chamber was filled but not circulated. Additional new fluid had to be added as testing progressed since edge delamination permitted seepage from the lower bonded area. For the salt water tests a drain was incorporated in the bottom of the chamber and a new solution was continuously introduced from the top by a drip system through a hypodermic needle. During the tests both fluids were noted to migrate by capillary action up the edge delaminations and matrix microcracks into the grip area. Heavy salt migration was noted in all delaminated areas, both submerged and above the fluid level. With this chamber both the specimen edges and surface, were exposed to the environments, the edges were never sealed. All specimens were allowed to soak in the environment for a minimum of 48 hours prior to load application. Tests were conducted on a two shift basis five days per week, the environments were not drained off during downtimes.

Coupled with the problems of delamination leakage, air/liquid interface concentration, and the insensitivity of tension-tension loading as a good indicator of matrix effects, testing was shifted to horizontally mounted specimens in tension-compression fatigue at a stress ratio of $R=-0.44$. Figure 2 shows a typical test setup with 1/3 span buckling restraints and a 25.4 mm gage length extensometer. Normally the desired fluid is slowly dripped in the center of the specimen for the duration of the test. These test were run on a three shift basis five days per week. During downtimes the drip system was turned off. Normally, however, tests were concluded with no downtimes. Fatigue tests in liquid environments on T300/934 were at 3 Hz, tests on AS/3501-6 were at 1 Hz. The same stress level, $-110 \rightarrow +248$ MPa was used on all 22 mm wide specimen tests. Prior to fatigue cycling an extensometer was placed on the specimen and strain measurements taken while a static load cycle was manually applied to obtain an initial static modulus. On some tests this was repeated at specific cyclic increments for the life of the specimen to evaluate stiffness changes. Dynamic strain data was also recorded and found to be identical to the static strain data.

To evaluate the effects of long term environmental exposure groups of AS/3501-6 specimens have been placed in different environments listed in Table I. Specimens will be tested at 1 year intervals for up to four years exposure in

tension-compression fatigue and static compression. In the freeze-thaw-humidity cycling, hydraulic fluid and jet fuel groups, five specimens marked precracked have been fatigued to 10,000 cycles (10% of average life) at $-110 \rightarrow +248$ MPa to produce major matrix microcracking in the $+45^\circ$ and 90° plies. Paths should exist for environmental penetration into the matrix to more accurately simulate service conditions without the prohibitive expense of long term environmental fatigue tests. These tests will be compared to life effects and weight gain of uncracked coupons soaked for the same time interval.

To correct the baseline data for any additional curing at room temperature that may occur during soaking in other environments, which would mask actual environmental effects, groups of specimens have been stored in the laboratory at controlled temperature and humidity for testing at yearly intervals.

Long term outdoor exposure tests have been conducted at numerous sea coast and high humidity sites. The semi-desert environment at the Lockheed Rye Canyon Laboratories provides an excellent site for high temperature exposure with low humidity. Groups of specimens have been mounted so that only one surface receives direct solar radiation. Temperatures measured on the specimens during summer months exceed 220°F .

Groups of specimens have been soaked in distilled water at room temperature with weight gain travelers.

A part of the NASA L-1011₄ Composite Vertical Fin program "Production Readiness Verification Testing" [4] is evaluating in the effects of long term thermal/humidity exposure (approximately 3 1/2 years) on structural elements under cyclic fatigue loading. At the end of the 3 1/2 years the structural elements will be statically tested and compared with similar elements tested at the beginning of the program. Groups of specimens have been placed in the same thermal/humidity environments to evaluate the effects on unloaded specimens. A schematic of the temperature-humidity cycle is shown in Figure 3. Normally the maximum temperature is 140°F per cycle, but over the 5800 thermal cycles applied in 3 1/2 years 40 cycles will go to 160°F and 10 cycles to 180°F . Relative humidity alternates between 95% and 0% on each cycle.

Phosphate ester hydraulics fluids present many compatibility problems with non-metallic materials. Short term exposure tests indicated effects on these epoxy matrices therefore long term exposures were begun in Skydrol LD-4 to determine if it could be used in areas where it might come into contact with composite structure.

Plans to evaluate composites for a wing application will require knowledge of the effects of fuel on the composite laminates since the design would probably utilize the wet wing concept. In addition to fuel exposure effects, operation in tropical environments will probably result in microbial growth in the fuel. Current metal wings employ coatings on the inner surfaces to prevent corrosion caused by microbial byproducts. These coatings are chemically similar to the epoxy matrix used in composites. MIL-C-27725B specifies a test for simulating the effects of such microbial byproducts. It consists of five parts of analytical-grade glacial acetic acid dissolved in 100 parts by weight of 3 percent sodium chloride in distilled water, placed in a container exposing 1/3 of the panel to the acid mixture, 1/3 to jet fuel, and 1/3 to the air-vapor mixture. Tests in both Jet A fuel and the mixture of Jet A, acetic acid, and salt water are proceeding.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Short Term Exposure Fatigue Effects

Tension-tension fatigue test results of 76 mm wide T300/934 specimens are presented in Figure 4. All specimens were tested at the same stress level and frequency. Specimens were fully immersed on edges and surfaces over most of the gage length. Failures of both the Skydrol and salt water tests occurred just at or above the liquid surface, not down in the continually fully immersed area.

For the salt water tests this failure zone corresponds to the maximum saline concentration area. As seen in Figure 4, no significant change in tension-tension fatigue life resulted from exposure to skydrol or salt water.

Further tests were conducted on T300/934 specimens in tension-compression fatigue at a stress ratio of $R = -0.44$ on smaller 22 mm wide specimens. For these tests in liquid contaminants a different test method was used. Instead of total continuous immersion the liquid was dripped on the center test section at specific increments of time so that drying would occur with the water solvent based fluids. This has the effect of increasing the concentration of the contaminant in the matrix, particularly where it wicks into a microcrack during the wet phase and dries, leaving behind a solid such as salt. Effects on life of this alternating wet-dry cycling are more damaging than being continuously wet. Results of these tests are presented in Figure 5. Results of baseline tests in laboratory air ($70 \pm 10^\circ\text{F}$, $50 \pm 10\%$ RH) were essentially the same at 3 and 10 Hz. To more closely simulate the environmental conditions aboard naval vessels, tests conducted in a 3.5% NaCl solution had H_2SO_4 added to the solution to give a pH of 3.5. This condition is encountered on non-nuclear vessels due to stack gas sorption in salt spray. Results on this laminate indicate no effect on fatigue life. Comparing the baseline mean life with tests in Jet A fuel indicates an increase in life by a factor of 2 in the fuel. Similarly, a phosphate ester hydraulic fluid, Skydrol LD-4, gave a life increase of at least a factor 9. Only one failure occurred in the Skydrol at 2.7×10^6 cycles, five other specimens were stopped after at least 2.35×10^6 cycles with no failure so that the true fatigue life increase was not established. Comparing the effects of Skydrol on tension-tension and tension-compression fatigue tests (Figure 4 versus Figure 5) demonstrates the lack of sensitivity of tension testing to environmental effects on the matrix. To identify the chemical producing the life increase tests were run in tributylphosphate ($(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_3\text{PO}$) a primary constituent of Skydrol. Results show a major increase in fatigue life. The apparent process for life increase is due to a plasticizing of the 934 epoxy since it is an aromatic compound and is soluble in a naptha ring material such as tributylphosphate. Both Jet-A and Skydrol contain aromatics which plasticize the matrix. The degree of life increase appears to be directly related to the plasticizer strength of the solvents that is, Skydrol is a better plasticizer than Jet-A. Compression tests of specimens soaked for 50 days in tributylphosphate show no change in modulus while fatigue tests of the same specimens show major life increases. Currently tests are still underway to characterize this effect.

A series of similar short term exposure fatigue tests were performed on AS/3501-6 specimens in tension-compression loading at the same stress level. All of the tests performed in liquids were at 1 Hz. These results are presented in Figure 6. Again no difference was found between 1 and 6 Hz tests in air. Results with 3 1/2% NaCl solution in distilled water showed a slight reduction in fatigue life. Tests with H_2SO_4 added to the 3 1/2% salt water solution reduced the fatigue life by approximately a factor of 4 from lab air.

Tests were conducted on AS/3501-6 specimens in tributylphosphate and tricresylphosphate to compare with the T300/934 results; no major effects on life were found. Some liquid environments might increase fatigue life if they could: 1) change the moisture content in the matrix; 2) cool any cyclic generated heat; 3) lubricate the plies, reducing potential wear damage; 4) plasticize the matrix. Tests conducted in hexane, which is not a matrix solvent, would provide cooling and not change the moisture balance showed no significant change. Salt water tests would have added moisture to the matrix but produced some life reduction. A series of specimens run in a penetrating oil showed a slight reduction in fatigue life. Why T300/934 was strongly affected by tributylphosphate and AS/3501-6 was not has yet to be determined.

Long Term Exposure Effects

Mechanical properties data for AS/3501-6 specimens exposed for 1 and 2 years in various environments are summarized in Table I. Included are ultimate compressive strengths, modulus, and fatigue life. Comparative fatigue life data

are presented in Figure 7. No significant changes were noted in compressive strengths for any of the exposures evaluated, the slight variations shown in Table I are within the data scatterband. Similar results were obtained with modulus data. Fatigue life comparisons however, do show some effects. Specimens stored for two years showed a slight increase in average life when compared to the original baseline, indicating some additional curing of the matrix. None of the material used in this investigation were post cured, therefore, additional curing is to be expected particularly in specimens subjected to elevated temperatures such as ones exposed outdoors and the freeze-thaw-humidity cycling groups. Indeed the group exposed for 2 years outdoors did have a life increase of almost a factor of two. Those in the freeze-thaw-humidity cycling group after 1 year demonstrated a life increase of a factor of 2 and after 2 years exposure an increase of over a factor of 3. With the thermal cycle used (Figure 3) the 1 year group experienced 1236 thermal cycles and the 2 year group 2543 thermal cycles. Of these totals in the 1 year group there were 10 cycles to 160°F and 5 cycles to 180°F, in the 2 year group there were 17 cycles to 160°F and 5 cycles to 180°F. Whether the life increase is due to plasticizing, additional curing, a residual stress relaxation, or a combination of each has not been determined. A one year soak in Skydrol LD-4 resulted in a slight increase in life, while a one year soak in Jet-A fuel had no effect. These data verify the short term results in tributylphosphate and tricresylphosphate where no plasticization of the AS/3501-6 occurred.

Two groups of specimens which had been loaded for 10,000 cycles prior to exposure to Jet-A fuel and Skydrol, however, resulted in reduced lives. The reduction in Jet-A fuel is slight, but life in Skydrol is less by a factor of 3. The precycling produces a network of matrix microcracks in the 90 and +45° plies which permit the fluids to wick through the matrix exposing a greater volume to the contaminant. Similar results have been reported for preloaded specimens exposed to environmental cycling^[5].

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the particular laminates tested in this study the following conclusions are believed to be valid:

1. The fatigue life of T300/934 is significantly increased by exposure to jet fuel and phosphate ester hydraulic fluids. One chemical responsible for the life increase has been identified as tributylphosphate.
2. Simulated stack gas in salt water is damaging to the fatigue life of AS3501-6.
3. AS/3501-6 specimens subjected to 2 years of freeze-thaw-humidity cycling demonstrated an increase in fatigue life.
4. Specimens precycled prior to exposure for 1 year in hydraulic fluid exhibited a reduction in fatigue life, whereas non-precycled ones had no reduction.

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TABLE I. LONG-TERM EXPOSURE TEST RESULTS

Environment	Year		
	0	1	2
Lab Air - Baseline			
F _{cu} (MPa)	406		
E (GPa)	55.2		
Fatigue life [1]	231,000		
Lab Storage			
F _{cu} (MPa)			461
E (GPa)			52.4
Fatigue life			336,000
Outdoor			
F _{cu} (MPa)			393
E (GPa)			53.1
Fatigue life			506,000
Water Immersion			
F _{cu} (MPa)		436	
E (GPa)		55.8	
Fatigue life		----	
Freeze-Thaw-Humidity Cycling			
F _{cu} (MPa)		447	
E (GPa)		56.5	53.1
Fatigue life		515,000	746,000
Jet Fuel			
F _{cu} (MPa)		----	
E (GPa)		53.8	
Fatigue life		205,170	
Fatigue life - Precracked		198,000	
Fuel and Acetic Acid + Salt Water			
F _{cu} (MPa)		432	
E (GPa)		53.8	
Fatigue life		----	
Skydrol			
F _{cu} (MPa)		406	
E (GPa)		53.8	
Fatigue life		399,000	
Fatigue life - Precracked		72,837	

[1] At -110 → + 248 MPa

Figure 1. Compression test fixture with 16 pin 8.8 mm column length buckling restraint

Figure 2. Tension - compression fatigue test setup with environment drip system attached

Figure 3. Freeze-thaw-humidity cycle

Figure 4. Effects of environment on the tension-tension fatigue life of T300/934. All specimens tested at the same stress level and at 3 Hz

Figure 5. Effects of environments on the tension - compression fatigue life of T300/934. All test run at a stress of $-110 \rightarrow +248$ MPa

Figure 6. Effects of environment on the tension - compression fatigue life of AS/3501-6. All test run at a stress of $-110 \rightarrow +248$ MPa

Figure 7. Fatigue test results for AS/3501-6 specimen exposed to various environments and time intervals. All tests run at the same stress level